

Surface Characterization and Adhesion of Torayca T-700G Carbon Fibers

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SUMMARY: Surface characterization of the Torayca T-700G high strength carbon fiber was undertaken with a view to evaluating and understanding adhesion to polymer matrices. Surface chemical analysis by XPS, surface free energy determination from dynamic contact angle, and microstructural characterization by STM was conducted and compared with before and after surface treatment of this fiber and with other PAN based high strength carbon fibers as well. It was found that the surface of the Torayca T-700G carbon fibers have higher O/C and N/C ratios than those of other PAN-based carbon fibers, such as the Hexcel IM7 and AS4. The free energy of the fibers appears slightly lower than those of IM7 and AS4. The single fiber fragmentation test was employed for adhesion measurements to various epoxy-amine thermoset systems and polycarbonate thermoplastic matrix. It was determined that adhesion of the carbon fiber to epoxy matrix is comparable or slightly lower than that of AS4 carbon fiber. Adhesion to polycarbonate matrix which is increased with higher processing temperatures, time and molecular weight of polycarbonate is at same level of AS4 fibers.

KEYWORDS: Torayca T-700G carbon fibers, carbon fiber surface characterization, single fiber fragmentation test, adhesion

INTRODUCTION

As a result of not only their high specific strength and modulus but also their decreasing cost, carbon fibers have been widely used as reinforcement in structural composite materials [1]. The carbon fiber mechanical properties have been responsible for their use in demanding severe service environments. Accompanying their performance, a more comprehensive and intensive understanding of carbon fiber surfaces and adhesion is needed to utilize their superior properties.

In this research, we have conducted surface analysis of the Torayca T-700G carbon fiber in order to better understand adhesion to thermoset and thermoplastic matrix composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Commercialized Torayca T-700G carbon fibers for this study were supplied by the manufacturer with non-surface treated (UT) and surface treated (ST). The fiber is the high strength type, and their typical properties are tensile strength of 4.9 GPa, modulus of 240 GPa and elongation of 2.0 %, respectively.

The fiber surface chemistry was evaluated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (Perkin-Elmer Physical Electronics PHI5400 spectrometer) with a monochromatic Mg X-ray source operated at 30 kV and 300 W with an emission current of 20 mA.

The advancing contact angles on the carbon fibers were measured by Dynamic Contact Analyzer (Cahn DCA 322) with water, formamide and diiodomethane [2]. All of the contact angles were obtained at an immersion speed of 20 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$, with a removing of initial 1 mm immersion data which can have fiber end effects. The fiber diameters for the contact angle determination were measured with non-polar hexane. The Owens-Wendt equation which is a linear equation in the form of $\gamma = mx + b$ with the slope “ m ” and intercept “ b ” given by the square root of the polar and dispersive components was used for free energy computation [2].

The topography of the fibers was evaluated by a Scanning Tunneling Microscope (Nanoscope III, Digital Instruments) with a type E piezo scan head and a commercial Pt-Ir tip (Nanotips[®]). To measure the topology of the fibers in the height data mode, scans were conducted keeping a constant tunneling current. Bias voltages and setpoint current were varied with range of 50-150 mV and 0.7-8.0 nA, respectively. 5 images with magnification of 300 nm (X) x 300 nm (Y) x 30 nm (Z) for the UT and ST fiber were collected to compute the surface roughness parameter R_a and the surface area of fibers.

To quantify the level of adhesion of the fibers to thermoset and thermoplastic matrix, the single fiber fragmentation test was employed. The single fiber fragmentation procedure is well described elsewhere [3]. The interpretation of the test results was based on the Kelly-Tyson approach $\tau = \sigma_f d / 2 l_c$ [4] (τ : *interfacial shear strength*, σ_f : *fiber tensile strength at the critical fiber fragmentation length*, d : *fiber diameter*, l_c : *critical fiber fragmentation length*). The single fiber fragmentation test process is shown in Figure 1. Tensile test coupon and testing apparatus are as shown in Figure 2 and 3. Two different kinds of Epoxy resin, diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A-based EPON[®] 828 & novolac EPON 160 (Shell Chemical Co.) were used for thermoset matrix composites. Three different amine curing agents, m-PDA (Aldrich Chemical), Jeffamine[®] D-230 and Jeffamine T-403 (Huntsman Corporation) were employed at stoichiometric concentrations with the epoxy matrices. Table 1 shows the combination of epoxy and curing agent with different curing cycles. Two kinds of pure polycarbonate with different molecular weight, Lexan[®] 8040 (GE Plastics, MW 24,894) and Polysciences polycarbonate (MW

32,000-36,000) were used for adhesion evaluation of the carbon fibers to thermoplastic matrix with different consolidation time and temperatures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Surface chemical analysis

XPS atomic ratios of Torayca T-700G carbon fibers are shown in Table 2. As shown in the table, O/C and N/C ratios increased by 120% and 190% respectively after surface treatment. These O/C and N/C atomic ratios in the ST carbon fiber are relatively higher than those of IM7,

Figure 2. Dimensional details of the single fiber fragmentation coupon

Figure 3. Single fiber fragmentation testing apparatus

Figure 1 Schematic representation of the single fiber fragmentation process

Table 1. Epoxy matrix single fiber fragmentation coupon composition and processing conditions.

Matrix	Curing Agent (phr)	Curing Cycle
EPON 828	m-PDA (14.5)	@75°C(2hr)→@125°C(2hr)
	T-403 (45.0)	@85°C(2hr)→@150°C(2hr)
	D-230 (35.0)	@80°C(2hr)→@125°C(3hr)
EPON 160	m-PDA (16.5)	@75°C(2hr)→@125°C(2hr)
	D-230 (37.5)	@80°C(2hr)→@125°C(3hr)

PANEX 33 [5] and AS4 carbon fiber [6, 7], which have been used frequently as model fibers for adhesion with polymer matrix. As the fibers are aged in the ambient environment, similar changes of carbon and oxygen concentration take place both carbon fibers.

Surface free energy

The fiber surface free energy of the fibers consisting of the dispersive (γ^d) and the polar component (γ^p) was obtained from the Owens-Wendt plot as seen in Table 3. As shown in the

Table 2. Surface analytical results of Torayca T-700G carbon fibers.

	Date	C	O	N	Si	O/C	N/C
UT Carbon Fiber	12/17/01	86.5	9.0	2.4	2.1	.104	.028
	03/25/02	87.2	7.6	2.5	2.6	.087	.029
	09/09/02	88.4	6.7	2.6	2.4	.076	.030
ST Carbon Fiber	12/17/01	75.7	17.4	6.2	0.7	.230	.082
	03/25/02	76.3	15.6	7.4	0.8	.204	.097
	09/09/02	77.3	14.9	7.0	0.9	.193	.091

table, the dispersive component of the free energy undergoes a marginal change after fiber surface treatment. On the other hand, the polar component shows increase of about 200% after the treatment. All of these numbers are relatively lower than those of IM6 [8] and AS4 [9] carbon fibers even though Torayca T-700G fibers demonstrate higher O/C and N/C ratios from the XPS results, as shown in Table 2.

Table 3. Surface free energy (mJ/ m²) of the carbon fibers from dynamic contact measurement.

Fibers	Dispersive	Polar	Total
UT Carbon Fiber	36.3	3.9	40.2
ST Carbon Fiber	38.9	11.7	50.6

Fiber topography

Figure 4 and 5 show STM images obtained at 300 nm x 300 nm scanning scale with 20 nm vertical range value for the UT and ST fibers. Both of the fibers have rippled surfaces

consisting of oval-shaped grains which form ribbon-like structure extending along the fiber axis in twisting each other. The oval-shaped grains in the UT fiber were measured by STM with average size about 20 nm x 11 nm in longer and shorter directions. In the ST fiber, the surface structure was observed with more rough surfaces which is giving 1.5 and 1.4 times increase of the surface roughness and surface area respectively, as shown in Table 4.

Figure 4. STM top view (left) and tilted view (right) image of UT carbon fiber.

Figure 5. STM top view (left) and tilted view (right) image of ST carbon fiber.

Table 4. Average surface roughness and surface area obtained from STM images.

Fiber	R_a (nm)	Area (nm ²) (300 nm x 300 nm area)
UT Carbon Fiber	1.2	100,734
ST Carbon Fiber	1.8	140,501

Adhesion: Epoxy matrix composites

Carbon fiber tensile strengths which are necessary for calculation the IFSS using the Kelly-Tyson equation were determined from the extrapolation of fiber tensile strength by the single fiber tensile test with gage length of 5mm, 10,, 25mm, and 50mm, as shown in Figure 6. This tensile strength tests were conducted by the Toray Carbon Co.

The IFSS of the Torayca T-700G carbon fibers to epoxy matrix are shown in Figure 7. In the UT carbon fiber, the IFSS are in the range of 35-42 MPa with a marginal change depending on the epoxy-amine matrix systems. On the other hand the ST fiber demonstrates 44-62 MPa of IFSS which means about 18-48% adhesion increase after fiber surface treatment. Among the different epoxy-curing agent systems EPON 160 / m-PDA system seems to have highest level of adhesion to the ST fiber. One of the reasons for the adhesion increment can be ascribed to the matrix shear modulus increase [9, 10]. From the DMA (Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer 2980, TA Instruments) modulus measurements, the adhesion increase is proportional to the matrix modulus with the relation of $(E_{fiber}/E_{matrix})^{0.7}$ and $(E_{fiber}/E_{matrix})^{0.5}$ for the UT and ST fibers, respectively. Comparing with the IFSS of AS4 and IM7 carbon fibers which are employed frequently for fiber adhesion experiments the Torayca T-700G UT and ST carbon fibers are seen to have slightly lower adhesion to EPON 828 / m-PDA system. [9, 11].

Figure 6. Tensile strength of Torayca T-700G carbon fibers

Adhesion: Polycarbonate matrix composites

The IFSS of the carbon fibers to polycarbonate matrix is shown in Figure 8 and 9. As shown, the consolidation temperature is found to have a significant influence on the adhesion,

especially more significant in lower molecular weight polycarbonate composites. As the consolidation temperature increases from 230°C to 310°C the adhesion increases in range of 30-36% and 13-15% for the Lexan 8040 and Polysciences PC, respectively. These results can be explained as due to enhanced adsorption of matrix polymer at higher processing and/or generation of a crystalline layer adjacent to the fibers, which is favorable for stress transfer [12]. Also it is seen that the increases of adhesion were achieved by 7-42% in the UT fiber and 20-35% in the ST fiber respectively with increasing molecular weight. This could be due to the increase in chain length and entanglement density on the fiber surface [13].

Figure 7. IFSS of Torayca T-700G carbon fiber in epoxy matrix composites by the single fiber fragmentation test.

Figure 8. IFSS of Torayca T-700G carbon fiber in Lexane 8040 polycarbonate with various consolidation temperatures at 120 psi for 20 min.

Figure 9. IFSS of Torayca T-700G carbon fiber in Polysciences polycarbonate with various consolidation temperatures at 120 psi for 20 min.

CONCLUSIONS

Surface characterization and adhesion performance of the Torayca T-700G carbon fibers to polymer matrices have been conducted, and the following conclusions are made.

1. Comparing with other PAN-based carbon fibers, two characteristics of the surface chemical properties of Torayca T-700G carbon fibers are demonstrated: (1) higher O/C and N/C ratios, (2) higher Si content than those of other PAN-based carbon fibers with commercial surface treatment
2. The topography of the T-700G carbon fibers evaluated by STM appears to consist of ribbon-like structures twisting along the fiber axis in twisting each other, similar to the surface microstructures of other PAN-based carbon fibers.
3. Adhesion of the T-700G fibers to the epoxy matrix (EPON 828/m-PDA) which is in range of 35-42 MPa and 44-62 MPa for UT and ST fibers is comparable or slightly lower than those of AS-4 fibers by the single fiber fragmentation test.
4. Adhesion of T-700G carbon fibers to polycarbonate is at similar level of AS-4 fibers, and increased as processing temperatures, time and molecular weight of polycarbonate are increased.

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REFERENCES

1. W. P. Hoffman, W. C. Hurley, T. W. Owens and H. T. Phan, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 1991, 26, pp 4545-4553.
2. F. Hoecker and J. Karger-Kocsis, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1996, 59, pp 139-153.
3. L. T. Drzal, M. J. Rich and P. F. Lloyd, *J. Adhesion*, 1982, 16, pp 1-30.
4. A. Kelly and W. R. V. Tyson, *Mech. Phys. Solid*, 1965, 32, pp 329-350.
5. C. L. Weitzsacker, Ming Xie and L. T. Drzal, *Surface and Interface Analysis*, 1997, 25, pp 53-63.
6. N. Dilsiz and J.P. Wightman, *Carbon*, 1999, 37, pp 1105-1114.
7. Long-Gui Tang and J. L. Kardos, *Polymer Comp.*, 1997, 18, pp 100-113.
8. L. T. Drzal, N. Sugira and D. Hook, *Composite Interfaces*, 1997, 4, pp 337-354.
9. M. B. Walther, K. L. Reifsnider, M. Madhukar and M. S. Genidy, *J. Compos. Technol. Research*, 2001, 23, pp 36-41.
10. H. L. Cox, *British J. Appl. Phys.*, 1952, 3, pp 72.
11. D. Bradford, K. Lease and Peter. M. A. Sherwood, *J. Compos. Technol. Res.*, 2000, 22, pp 53-59.
12. R. L. Brady and R. S. Porter, *J. Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 1989, 2, pp 164-171.
13. V. K. Raghavendran, M. M. Waterbury, V. Rao and L. T. Drzal, *J. Adhesion Sci. Technol.*, 1997, 11, pp 1501-1512